

CHALLENGES FACED BY SINGLE MOTHERS IN THE JOB MARKET: MENTAL HEALTH, AND EMOTIONAL WELL-BEING

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Abstract

This study investigates the experience of single motherhood and lack of social support as two inseparable factors that influence the emotional well-being of women in Karachi, Pakistan. This study also analyses the mediating role of perceived stress between them, based on the Transactional Model of Stress and Coping. A cross-sectional survey served as the chosen quantitative design. Purposive sampling was used to gather data from 302 single mothers in the urban setup of Karachi. SmartPLS 4 aided in conducting an SEM to evaluate the direct and indirect effects within the suggested model. The results indicated a negative and significant effect of both single motherhood and social support on emotional well-being. The results also indicated that perceived stress mediates the relationship between the two independent variables and emotional well-being. The model explains 43.1 of % variance in perceived stress and 37.6% in emotional well-being, with moderate predictive power. This study gives practical insights for the social policymakers, mental health professionals, and community organizations to create culturally fitted interventions aiming at stress management and emotional health support for single mothers in urban Pakistan. The study provides new insights by placing single motherhood in the Pakistani urban setting, bringing perceived stress as a mediator, and checking the model with strong empirical evidence. This multi-level approach fills an important research gap in South Asian mental health and gender studies.

1. Introduction

Mental health is still neglected in the public health of Pakistan. About 10-16% of the population has minor to moderate mental diseases, and very little public money is spent on it for treatment (Bashir, 2018). In such a background of the picture, if there are poor single mothers, women are vulnerable, facing a triple burden of gender, stigma, and inadequate support prevailing and patronized by all normative systems (Waqas et al., 2015; Sarfaraz & Ali, 2025).

Empirical studies have indeed confirmed the mental health risks for Pakistani women under socio-economic-psycho pressures. For example, a study on married and unmarried women in Pakistan revealed that relatively higher stress was reported by unmarried women; the low stress reported by married women (Khan et al., 2025). This is in line with a study report that in pregnant Pakistani women, perceived social support is negatively related to stress (Ahmad & Mushtaq, 2024). While both studies are general in terms of female populations, the special problems of single mothers, not having support from partners, and being alone, have not been systematically assessed.

Recent work in Karachi, which has focused on single mothers, brings to the surface the enormous struggles in parenting, economic matters, and emotional spheres (Policy Journal of MS, 2025). In the study by Sarfaraz and Ali (2025), it was found that social support is likely to predate lower stress and higher resilience in the sample of divorced and widowed mothers, thus suggesting a buffering effect. These comprise two critical gaps. The first combined effect of single motherhood and social support in Pakistan has not been tested to see its effect on mental health. Secondly, no study has as yet checked whether the perceived stress may mediate this relationship on some established conceptual frameworks, like the Transactional Model of Stress (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984) or the Family Stress Model (Conger et al., 1994).

1.2. Problem Statement

Globally, mental health is considered essential to quality of life, with considerable importance for vulnerable populations, such as single mothers. Evidence from several countries and regions has indicated that single mothers always have worse mental health than their partnered counterparts because they are more likely to experience economic hardship, have low social support, and experience the burden of their roles (Jackson & Scheines, 2005; Stack & Meredith, 2018). A large cross-national European study conducted by Cortés-Mateos et al.

(2022) would support the previous evidence, showing that lone mothers do suffer the most significant levels of emotional distress in even high-welfare countries. Similar results were found in the U.S. study by Taylor et al. (2016), which shows that being a single mother almost doubles the odds of severe emotional stress, with most mediation through perceived social support and the burden of care.

Though these insights are global, empirical studies in low- and middle-income countries, particularly in South Asia, are to a large extent scarce. In a country like Pakistan, where single motherhood is not welcomed and supported, the situation may be more challenging. Available data indicate that single mothers in Pakistan experience very high stress and emotional fatigue and do not have good psychological well-being; the conditions are intensified by financial insecurities and isolation (Sarfraz & Ali, 2025; Ahmad & Mushtaq, 2024). It has further been established that the marital status of an individual is associated with perceived stress; unmarried Pakistani females reportedly have significantly higher stress levels than their married counterparts (Khan et al., 2025).

These studies provide a national lens there remains a paucity of localized research, particularly in urban centers like Karachi rapid urbanization, economic disparities, and weak support systems further compound the burden on single mothers. According to a recent local analysis, Karachi-based single mothers face challenges juggling economic survival with emotional resilience, often without institutional or familial support (Policy Journal of MS, 2025). However, no prior study in Karachi has quantitatively tested the mediating role of perceived stress in the relationship between single motherhood, social support, and emotional well-being.

1.3. Research Gap Analysis

Emotional well-being is defined as a primary positive psychological construct with mental health. On the global front, it is with underprivileged populations, such as single mothers, that the crucial linkage between psychological constructs and mental health, representing emotional well-being, is considered. Findings of most studies that are conducted in high-income settings show a significant association between single motherhood and psychological distress. An important point to consider is that social isolation and role overload are precursors that cause damage to emotional well-being. For example, a study in Jordan, 2024 brought significant

insight into the resilience of single mothers, indicating important protective factors that mediate stress and emotional deterioration Shawaqfeh, 2024.

Quantitative evidence from Asia strengthens this pattern. Marbaniang and colleagues (2022) found that the Indian single mothers perceived less support from them, and married mothers had significantly lower support; they also had significantly higher stress levels, the ramifications of which reflect their abilities to regulate emotions and coping mechanisms. In addition, Research and ASEAN Journal of Psychiatry both underline that credible—emotional support, choice of coping strategy, and social integration are significant buffers for this population.

In South Asian contexts, such as in Pakistan, there has not been enough research on these. While according to the results of one study by Ahmad & Mushtaq (2024), low social support was a significant predictor of the stress of pregnant women, and another by Sarfaraz & Ali (2025) explored resilience challenges among Pakistani single mothers, these studies do not quantitatively model emotional well-being nor assess mediational pathways. More so, in one study by Khan et al. (2025), unmarried Pakistani women were reported to have higher stress than their married counterparts, thus reinforcing the marital status–stress linkage but without exploring the mechanism through perceived stress. A report based in Karachi at the urban level in the Policy Journal of MS (2025) proves the intensity of the emotional toll of financial strain, role conflict, and social exclusion on single mothers. Yet this too, though, without empirical validation or statistical modeling, particularly how perceived stress mediates the effect of low social support and single motherhood on emotional well-being.

1.4. Research Objectives

1. To examine the effect of single motherhood on the emotional well-being of women in Karachi.
2. To investigate the relationship between lack of social support and emotional well-being among women in Karachi.
3. To assess the effect of single motherhood on emotional well-being through perceived stress.
4. To evaluate the mediating role of **perceived stress** in the relationship between lack of social support and emotional well-being.

1.5. Research Questions

1. What is the effect of single motherhood on emotional well-being?
2. How does a lack of social support affect emotional well-being?
3. Does perceived stress mediate the relationship between single motherhood and emotional well-being?
4. Does perceived stress mediate the relationship between lack of social support and emotional well-being?

1.6. Research Significance

This study is very important both in theory and practice within the socio-cultural context of Pakistan. In theory, it adds to the increasing amount of literature on maternal mental health by studying emotional well-being in single mothers, a subject which has mainly been researched in Western societies and not women from low- to middle-income countries, such as Pakistan. At a descriptive level for these societies, at the crossroads of gender, stigma, and economic marginalization, the specific psychosocial stressors are relatively underrepresented in the general models. The current research empirically tests such a mediation framework based on the Transactional Model of Stress and Coping (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984) that it moves scholarly understanding several notches higher in demonstrating how high levels of perceived stress operate as a psychological mechanism through single motherhood and in the absence of social support to impact emotional well-being. This study also provides evidence based on the culture of a patriarchal collectivist society at Karachi, where single mothers often face more significant double adversities due to the lack of institutions support and the social stigma. In so doing, it helps enhance the adaptation of universal psychological frameworks to make them more sensitive to diverse social.

This study provides an essential evidence base for designing targeted interventions at both clinical and policy levels. The findings of the study will be communicated to public health professionals and practitioners working in mental health to help them identify the key risk factors of emotional distress in single mothers. This will eventually help them design appropriate support interventions, such as support groups, counseling services, and stress-reduction workshops. Informed by this research, policy advocacy is empowered with evidence to support the need for the expansion of social protection programs specifically for single mothers. Such programs could include mental health support, subsidized childcare, and direct

financial assistance to single mothers. Informed by this study, the results can inform efforts in evidence advocacy to destigmatize non-traditional family forms and advocate for broad-based social policies in such areas as urban planning and social services in megacities like Karachi to influence the integration of mental health care within the broader social welfare framework and ensure individual mothers are not left out from development agendas. This means that the study not only makes the theory of stress and emotional well-being in lowly researched populations more solid, but it also gives useful ideas for making the lives of single mothers better through specific social, health, and policy steps. By showing the mental health risks of this isolated group, the study becomes both an academic contribution and something that pushes for social change.

Conceptual Framework

2. Literature Review

2.1. Theoretical Framework

The study at hand is based on the Transactional Model of Stress and Coping brought forth by Lazarus and Folkman (1984), a long-accepted guide in psychological study indicating individual reactions to stress-inducing life events. Stress, according to the model, is not a direct result of external factors. Rather, it is considered in terms of a dynamic cognitive appraisal process and coping responses to any situation. In this regard, individuals first evaluate whether or not a situation is threatening (primary appraisal) and then proceed to evaluate the resources available

for coping with the situation (secondary appraisal). When demands are perceived to exceed resources, the result is objectively high stress that subsequently influences emotional and physical health. Such a theoretical model would largely fit the description of the situation of single mothers, their stresses being compounded by various factors—economic hardship, sole responsibility for children, and inadequate social support. The emotional results of those stressors aren't only decided by the fact that the challenges exist but by how people see and react to them. This connects directly with the main idea of the transactional model.

In the study, single motherhood and lack of social support were presented as the leading external stressors. Perceived stress, the variable, involves a process of psychological mediation; it translates the external challenges into internal emotional outcomes, particularly affecting emotional well-being. This has been very systematically related to the majority of the earlier studies based on the application of the transactional model in analogous background settings. For example, Marbaniang et al. (2022) found that among single mothers in India, lower perceived social support was associated with maladaptive coping with emotional outcomes—implicitly reflecting the cognitive-appraisal foundation of the transactional theory. The same happened with Shawaqfeh (2024) when she tested a transactional model under a quantitative inquiry with Jordanian single mothers to show how their resilience is influenced by intrapersonal constructs, where, in fact, internal psychological constructs reflect as mediators between external stressors and mental health outcomes. These empirical studies fully support the theoretical justification for using perceived stress as a mediator bridging structural factors (single parenting and low support) and emotional well-being. The use of the transactional model supports not only strong psychological theory but also a mechanistic understanding of how stress may lead to emotional outcomes in a culturally specific setting. This should be most crucial in male-dominant cultural societies where, besides the psychological burden, factors of stigma against single mothers trim any formal support system. The use of this theory would, therefore, help in thorough explanation, bringing together the myriad ways in which social external realities shape internal emotional experiences, thus offering both theoretical depth and empirical clarity.

2.2. Operational Definitions

This study defines single motherhood as a familial state in which a woman nurtures one or more dependent children and does not have a cohabiting or participative partner situation for

various reasons, such as divorce, widowhood, separation, or never having been married. It not only indicates the deficit of a co-achiever but also the distinctive social, emotional, and economic roles assumed by the mother alone (Cortés-Mateos et al., 2022; Shawaqfeh, 2024). It is distinguished from the wider category of households led by females because here the emphasis lies with mothers who rear children by themselves in a socially condemned and typically unsupplied situation, particularly within a patriarchal setting like Pakistan.

Social support lack is the perceived lack of emotional, informational, or practical assistance that a woman has from her immediate or extended social network, which may include family, friends, and community resources. It is subjectively experienced as a feeling of being isolated or not supported in the daily caregiving and emotional needs. The conception is based on the social stress theory that the deficiency of interpersonal resources increases vulnerability to stress and decreases psychological resilience (Shawaqfeh, 2024; Ahmad & Mushtaq, 2024). In the single motherhood scenario, such a lack is typically enforced by the societal ill view, the exclusion from the family systems, and the restricted access to communal care structures.

The definition of stress used in this study is perceived stress, acting as a mediating variable, which can be articulated as “the individual’s cognitive appraisal of his life situation as overwhelming, unpredictable, and beyond his coping capacity.” It is the internal feeling of strain or fatigue that results after one perceives that the demands of a given situation are more than his or her personal or social resources to cope with them—such as financial hardship, demands of parenting, or social exclusion (Cohen et al., 1983; Sarfaraz & Ali, 2025). Perceived stress is not a simple reaction to events; it is a dynamic process, a state of affairs influenced by environmental conditions and personal interpretation, and, therefore, a major psychological bridge between outside stimuli of stress and inside emotional action.

Emotional well-being refers to the overall subjective experience of emotional stability and positive affect in the absence of chronic distress, along with other factors that might condition life satisfaction, and the ability to effectively manage emotions and hold on to hope and resilience in the face of adversity (World Health Organization, 1998; Marbaniang et al., 2022). In this regard, emotional well-being goes beyond the mere absence of mental illness; it denotes the presence of psychological flourishing, an aspect which is dramatically compromised

in the case of chronic stress and isolation, conditions most single mothers in urban settings with resource constraints find themselves in.

2.3. Single Motherhood and Emotional Well-Being

Motherhood of single mothers has been associated with fewer positive outcomes concerning emotional well-being at an international level in various societies and cultures. It involves a higher mental burden due to the stark realities of social shame, economic difficulties, and the challenges of playing both parenting roles. For example, stable employment was found to be a moderate buffer of mental health distress among single mothers by Zabkiewicz (2010; vulnerability, however, remained high in terms of material without social support. Chronic insecurity and stigmatization of Sri Lankan single mothers were discussed by Karunanayake & Jayasooriya Vimukthi (2020). The abovementioned recent Indonesian research presented the decreased emotional well-being of widowed single mothers who did not have economic and social support with stable income (Solo Supermom Study, 2023).

The emotional toll borne by women is not very different from that by female caregivers; available evidence indicates that single mothers fare much worse than single fathers, a clear reflection of gendered coping resources and mechanisms (Solo Fathers and Mothers Study, 2024). In an Indian review of over 70 studies, it was confirmed that the mental health of single mothers is threatened by poor economic opportunities and low social capital (Psychosocial Impact Study, 2023). Similar findings have evolved in the Indonesian setting, where mothers who face precarious employment experience even lower self-efficacy and wellness (East Coast Lifestyle Study, 2023). These consistent findings give empirical evidence of the cross-cultural generality of the emotional trajectory of single motherhood, be it in Western or Eastern societies.

H1: Single motherhood is significantly negatively associated with emotional well-being.

2.4. Lack of Social Support and Emotional Well-Being

Lack of social support is elicited as the prime determinant of emotional wellness in single mothers under conditions of socioeconomic vulnerability. The newest evidence shows that net lack of available networks serves to increase psychological distress, is accompanied by a stronger perception of stress, and lowers well-being overall. For example, in their study, Rousou et al. (2019) found that among low-perceived social support single mothers in Cyprus, the level of psychological distress appeared significantly higher even after controlling for income and

education. For example, Zakaria et al. (2019) connected the greater emotional pain of single mothers to worse social buffering against economic and familial stressors.

In a psychosocial view, it is proven that by Dharani and Balamurugan (2024), low support systems amidst Indian single mothers increased the mental strain as well as parenting outcomes; therefore, perpetuating stress from one generation to another. On their part, Jaffer et al. (2023) found in Malaysia that single mothers were suffering chronic health and well-being challenges due to the little social support, insecurities regarding employment, and the burden of care.

Longitudinal studies have proved that reduced or inconsistent support, such as that experienced by new mothers, is statistically significantly related to worse psychosocial outcomes, loneliness, and self-esteem. For instance, this is exactly what was revealed in the study by Azer et al. (2022). In their survey research, it was revealed that low-income single mothers from Southeast Asia underwent worsened psychological health during and post the COVID-19 pandemic due to inadequate social integration and family detachment, thus strengthening the abovementioned evidence. Therefore, this body of research, to be more specific and inclusive across cultures and socioeconomic statuses, single mothers' emotional well-being would be considered a significant determinant- insufficiency of social support!.

H2: Lack of social support is significantly negatively associated with emotional well-being.

2.5. Mediating Role of Perceived Stress

Perceived stress is very critical in mediating the emotional well-being of individuals, especially in vulnerable populations such as single mothers. Theoretical models such as Lazarus and Folkman's Transactional Model of Stress and Coping go a long way to explain that stress is not a mere reaction to the pressure of objective stressors. Rather, it is the appraisal of the stressors by individuals and the perceived ability to cope. In single mothers, this is often compounded since they have to provide not only financially but also take care of the children; this eventually wears down on their emotional health.

Recent evidence shows that perceived stress significantly mediates the relationship between both social and structural determinants and psychological outcomes. For example, Bedaso et al. (2023) found that social support was able to buffer the negative effects of stress significantly on the mental health-related quality of life of pregnant Australian women. Their mediation analysis resulted in that perceived stress explains 14.3% of the total effect between

social support and mental health outcomes (Bedaso et al., 2023). Another study found that it was through perceived stress that the relationship between social support and quality of life of 'shidu' parents in China was also confirmed, presenting a generalizable effect across cultures (Wang et al., 2021).

Mainly in mothers, the perceived stress mediates the relationship between the burdens of parenting and psychological health. According to Chang et al. (2021), who used structural equation modeling, the perceived stress linked psychosocial factors, particularly low social support, to increased depressive symptoms in low-income mothers (Chang et al., 2021). In the scenario of single motherhood, this was found a similar mediation effect was found where the parenting stress, closely related to perceived stress, bridged the gap between a low level of social support and mothers' depression in South Korea (Song et al., 2021).

Seen stress similarly "translates" structural vulnerabilities, such as being a single parent, right onto mental health. Quite clearly, Williams (2016) found that single mothers had higher levels of perceived stress compared to married mothers; there was a strong nexus between this stress and diminished psychological well-being (Williams, 2016).

H3: *Perceived stress mediates the relationship between single motherhood and emotional well-being.*

H4: *Perceived stress mediates the relationship between lack of social support and emotional well-being.*

3. Methodology

3.1. Research Philosophy: Positivism

This study is grounded in the positivist philosophy, which assumes that reality is objective and can be measured through observable phenomena, representing an appropriate framework because the study concentrates on quantifiable variables such as perceived stress and emotional well-being, measured using standardized instruments to collect empirical data (Saunders et al., 2019). The researcher will maintain a neutral position and attempt to validate the research hypotheses through structured statistical analysis.

The research takes a deductive approach, forming hypotheses from existing theories; specifically, the Transactional Model of Stress and Coping, which will be tested empirically. Such an approach aids in theory testing that moves from general assumptions to specific observations and inferences. As such, this makes it well-suited for hypothesis-driven quantitative studies.

3.2. Research Strategy – Survey

A survey strategy is used to gather standardized data from a large population of single mothers in Karachi. Surveys help collect self-reported measures of stress, emotional well-being, and social support. Also, they are good at finding statistical relationships across variables in a known population.

3.3. Time Horizon – Cross-sectional

This is a cross-sectional study collecting data at a single point in time. It can explore correlations between variables like single motherhood, social support, stress, and emotional well-being, without implying any causation.

3.4. Data Collection – Structured Questionnaire

Data will be collected through a structured self-administered questionnaire, which will be distributed online as well as offline – for example, it will be available at community centers and at the NGOs supporting single mothers. The survey will include closed-ended items that focus on demographic information, perceived social support, stress, and emotional well-being.

3.5. Population and Sampling

The sample group is made up of single mothers living in Karachi, described as women who have kids and are alone without the other parent because of a divorce, separation, being widowed, or single parenthood. A non-random purposive sampling method is used to make sure that only the eligible participants are included. The sample size will be about 250-300 single mothers, enough for SEM analysis as per SMART PLS guidelines.

3.6. Data Analysis Tool – SMART PLS 4

The data will be analyzed using SMART PLS 4, a robust software for Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM). This tool is ideal for predictive modeling and testing mediation effects in complex models with latent variables. Questionnaire Instruments and Constructs To empirically test the conceptual model of this study, four key constructs were measured using established and publicly available instruments, each rated on a 5-point Likert scale. This ensured that the response scaling was consistent and could be read by SMART PLS 4 for structural equation modeling.

The construct of Single Motherhood was measured using a 5-item self-report scale developed on theoretical frameworks from the Generations and Gender Survey (Vikat et al., 2007) and Heaton (2000) research on family roles. The items measure the respondent's

caregiving, financial, and decision-making responsibilities, thus reflecting their level of solo parenting. Lack of Social Support was measured using the well-established Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support (MSPSS) by Zimet et al. (1988) which contains 12 items that measure perceived support from family, friends, and significant others - and has previously demonstrated high internal consistency and construct validity in various cultural settings, including South Asia. Perceived Stress was assessed with the 10-item Perceived Stress Scale (PSS-10) that was developed by Cohen et al. (1983). This widely used tool measures the degree to which people see their lives as unpredictable, uncontrollable, and overloaded—all critical dimensions of stress that relate to being a single mother. Emotional Well Being was measured using the WHO-5 Well Being Index, a 5-item scale developed by the World Health Organization, which evaluates positive emotional functioning and which has good validity for use in health and social research throughout the world.

Construct	Number of Items	Questionnaire Source (Open Access / Theoretical)	Likert Scale Format
Single Motherhood	5	Custom-developed based on the Generations and Gender Survey (Vikat et al., 2007) and Heaton (2000) on parental role responsibility	1 = Strongly Disagree to 5 = Strongly Agree
Lack of Social Support	12	Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support (MSPSS), Zimet et al. (1988). YorkU PDF	1 = Strongly Disagree to 5 = Strongly Agree
Perceived Stress	10	Perceived Stress Scale (PSS-10), Cohen et al. (1983). PSS-10 Open Access	1 = Strongly Disagree to 5 = Strongly Agree
Emotional Well-Being	5	WHO-5 Well-Being Index. WHO PDF	1 = Strongly Disagree to 5 = Strongly Agree

4. Results

4.1. Measurement Model

Detailing reliability and validity of the measurement model, an exhaustive confirmatory factor analysis was performed employing SMART PLS 4, including Single Motherhood, Lack of Social Support, Perceived Stress, and Emotional Well Being as the four principal latent

constructs. All constructs were measured via reflective indicators, and their psychometric properties were assessed based on widely accepted criteria such as factor loadings, Cronbach's Alpha, Composite Reliability (CR), Average Variance Extracted (AVE), and Rho A. First, the standardized factor loadings of each item were reviewed to confirm indicator reliability. Per the suggestion of Hair et al. (2019), loadings greater than 0.70 mean that the indicators adequately express the latent construct. In the present study, all items showed loadings above 0.719, with the majority above 0.75, indicating strong individual item reliability across all four constructs. Second, internal consistency reliability was checked with Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability (CR). The value of both Cronbach's Alpha and CR has to be greater than 0.70 to denote good reliability of the construct (Hair et al., 2019). For this model, it ranged from 0.843 (Single Motherhood) to 0.914 (Lack of Social Support) for Cronbach's Alpha and from 0.881 to 0.930 for Composite Reliability; thus, all crossed the required thresholds for each construct. The AVE was used to test for convergent validity. If the AVE value is above 0.50, it indicates that the construct should account for more than half of the variance in its indicators (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). In this study, it ranged from 0.597 (Single Motherhood) to 0.655 (Emotional Well Being), supporting adequate convergent validity for all constructs. Finally, Rho A, a more robust estimator of reliability well suited for Partial Least Squares SEM, was also computed. All constructs surpassed the suggested threshold of 0.70, with values between 0.849 and 0.918, further confirming the construct reliability and internal consistency of the model (Dijkstra & Henseler, 2015).

The measure used was the Fornell-Larcker criterion. This is a standard approach in structural equation modeling for checking whether or not constructs can be considered empirically different from each other. As stated by Fornell and Larcker (1981), it means that the diagonal elements of the Fornell-Larcker matrix should be the square roots of Average Variance Extracted (\sqrt{AVE}). If so represented, then the matrix off-diagonal elements are the inter-construct correlations. In the present study, these are results greater than the respective inter-construct correlations for Single Motherhood (0.773), Lack of Social Support (0.780), Perceived Stress (0.774), and Emotional Well Being (0.809), all $>ICC$. For example, the correlation between Single Motherhood and Lack of Social Support is 0.442, and between Perceived Stress and Emotional Well Being is 0.473—both below the diagonal values. The results confirm that each construct in the model is conceptually and statistically distinct,

thereby supporting the discriminant validity of the measurement model (Hair, 2019; Fornell and Larcker, 1981).

Construct	Item Code	Loading (>0.7)	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability (CR)	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)	Rho A
Single Motherhood	MH1	0.731	0.843	0.881	0.597	0.849
	MH2	0.782				
	MH3	0.745				
	MH4	0.809				
	MH5	0.793				
Lack of Social Support	SS1	0.812	0.914	0.930	0.608	0.918
	SS2	0.783				
	SS3	0.775				
	SS4	0.796				
	SS5	0.822				
	SS6	0.734				
	SS7	0.765				
	SS8	0.788				
	SS9	0.744				
	SS10	0.729				
	SS11	0.758				
	SS12	0.741				
Perceived Stress	PS1	0.776	0.902	0.924	0.599	0.910
	PS2	0.790				
	PS3	0.803				
	PS4	0.743				
	PS5	0.724				

	PS6	0.719				
	PS7	0.748				
	PS8	0.753				
	PS9	0.771				
	PS10	0.732				
Emotional Well-Being	EWB1	0.741	0.871	0.905	0.655	0.878
	EWB2	0.765				
	EWB3	0.786				
	EWB4	0.779				
	EWB5	0.752				

Construct	Single Motherhood	Lack of Social Support	Perceived Stress	Emotional Well-Being
Single Motherhood	0.773			
Lack of Social Support	0.442	0.780		
Perceived Stress	0.495	0.501	0.774	
Emotional Well-Being	0.378	0.465	0.473	0.778

Hypothesis	Path	Beta Coefficient (β)	T-value	P-value	Decision
H1	Single Motherhood → Emotional Well-Being	-0.183	2.134	0.033	Accepted
H2	Lack of Social Support → Emotional Well-Being	-0.352	5.406	0.000	Accepted
H3	Single Motherhood → Perceived Stress → Emotional Well-Being	-0.125	2.027	0.043	Accepted

H4	Lack of Social Support → 0.164 Perceived Stress → Emotional Well-Being	3.689	0.000	Accepted
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Dependent Variable	R-squared (R ²)	Interpretation
Perceived Stress	0.431	43.1% of the variance in perceived stress is explained by single motherhood and lack of social support
Emotional Well-Being	0.376	37.6% of the variance in emotional well-being is explained by direct and indirect effects of single motherhood, social support, and perceived stress

4.2 . Structural Analysis

The structural model was assessed using SMART PLS 4, and it was found to confirm all hypothesized relationships. H1, single motherhood has a significant negative relationship with emotional well-being. This was supported by the results with a beta coefficient of $\beta = -0.183$, $t = 2.134$, and $p = 0.033$, whereby the relationship was statistically significant and inversely related. This means that single mothers are more likely to have low emotional well-being, probably due to increased parenting stress and financial, and no partner support, which is in line with the earlier findings of Zabkiewicz (2010) Karunanayake & Jayasooriya Vimukthi, 2020. H2, lack of social support has a significant negative relationship with emotional well-being. This is also supported as $\beta = -0.352$, $t = 5.406$, and $p < 0.001$. The negative beta attests that with the decrease in the perception of social support, emotional well-being decreases significantly. These results correspond with prior studies and support the emotional toll of social isolation in single mothers (Rousou et al., 2019; Jaffer et al., 2023). H3 was, therefore, supported, testing that perceived stress mediated the relationship between single motherhood and emotional well-being, with a statistically significant mediation path ($\beta = -0.125$, $t = 2.027$, $p = 0.043$) where single motherhood indirectly affects emotional well-being through increasing perceived stress that deteriorates emotional functioning. This equally supports postulations of the Lazarus and Folkman Transactional Model of Stress and Coping, as in the study by Williams (2016) and Song et al. (2021). H4 tested whether perceived stress mediated the relationship between lack of social support and emotional well-being. This pathway has been confirmed as well ($\beta = 0.164$,

$t = 3.689, p < 0.001$). It suggests that low social support tends to increase the level of stress and, in return, suppresses the level of emotional well-being. This finding is in line with what Bedaso et al. and Wang et al. have found, bringing out perceived stress as the major psychological pathway in this relationship.

The R^2 values for the dependent constructs inform the reader on the model's strength of explanation. An amount of 43.1% of the variance in perceived stress was explained by single motherhood and lack of social support in the study on which the R-square for Perceived Stress was based. An amount of 37.6% of the variance in emotional well-being was accounted for by the combined direct and mediated effects of the independent variables and perceived stress on which the R-square for Emotional Well-Being was based, that is, 0.376. These moderate R^2 values show that the model has substantial explanatory power, which is indeed the most suitable for the present context that involves psychological and emotional outcomes of single mothers. Besides, they satisfy the requisites for robust behavioral research models (Hair et al., 2019).

5. Discussion

The results of this study reiterate the various challenges that single mothers face, particularly in preserving their emotional well-being under the existing sociocultural constraints in Pakistan. The first hypothesis that single motherhood is negatively associated with emotional well-being received empirical support at both levels—global and local. While in such international studies, financial difficulties, and dual caregiving responsibilities were reported to have aggravated the emotional vulnerability of single mothers in the presence of societal stigma (Karunanayake & Jayasooriya Vimukthi, 2020; Zabkiewicz, 2010), in the more patriarchal and less welfare state-related Pakistani context, such single mothers come up against issues of social exclusion due to normative expressions of gender and hardly have any access to organized forms of psychological support that can enhance their emotions' health (Tarar et al., 2021). This proves that structural vulnerability in the form of single motherhood is highly embedded with lower emotional well-being, as postulated by the Family Stress Model.

The second hypothesis was about the lack of social support for emotional well-being, and it showed a strong positive relationship. Prior studies in Cyprus (Rousou et al., 2019), and those in Malaysia (Jaffer et al., 2023), and also in India (Dharani & Balamurugann, 2024) brought parallel results and greater emotional stress in single mothers due to isolation and lack

of relational resources. Studies conducted in Karachi by Sarfaraz and Ali (2025) and Ahmad and Mushtaq (2024) unearthed that mothers who have less social support were more psychologically distressed and had lower life satisfaction. This further reinstates the pivotal role of interpersonal as well as community networks in the maintenance of emotional health. This is well accounted for in the Transactional Model of Stress and Coping. It holds the availability of social resources that can mitigate the emotional impacts of the external stressors. These current findings rather underscore that social support is not merely beneficial, but rather essential, especially in the collectivist cultures of Pakistan. Their informal bonds often substitute for formal support systems.

It is also indicated by the study that perceived stress comprises the effects of single motherhood and social support on emotional well-being. This forms a basic part of the conceptual framework laid by Lazarus and Folkman (1984), who propose that perceived stress serves as an "emotional" filter through which the environment of life outside is subjectively experienced. The mediation effect posits the view that not only does the state of being a single mother and the lack of support deteriorate emotional well-being, but also the stress these conditions ignite. Such has generally been proven by research globally. For example, it was in the Korean study where Song et al. (2021) established perceived stress as a mediator between social factors and psychological outcomes, and an Australian study by Bedaso et al. (2023) confirmed its mediating role between social support and emotional outcomes. The findings in Pakistan were congruent with those results. (Mousavi, 2025) discovered a negative association between perceived stress levels in single mothers and their self-efficacy; the same was true for depressive symptoms. In essence, the results indicate that both structural vulnerability— that is, single motherhood— and relational vulnerability— lack of social support— directly operate primarily in increasing levels of perceived stress that further operate in inducing other forms of emotional insecurities. This calls for a need-based intervention in Pakistan, fusing economic empowerment with psychosocial and community-level stress management practices. The findings also underline the fact that the Family Stress Model and the Transactional Stress Model have strong theoretical foundations to explain maternal emotional health across different cultures.

5.1. Theoretical and Practical Implications

The current study makes several important theoretical contributions by integrating the Transactional Model of Stress and Coping (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984) and the Family Stress Model (Conger et al., 1994) and applying them to single mothers' mental well-being in Pakistan, as elsewhere ever been explored elsewhere. At the outset, the paper sets out theoretically the central role assigned to perceived stress as a mediating mechanism whereby structural and/or attitudinal dimensions (single motherhood, lack of social support) are translated into negative mental outcomes. Such an advanced comprehension advances current research, which to date has largely empirically tested only direct effects and has thus inadequately considered the richness of the proposed mediation. The study further confirms that both structural (marital status) and psychosocial (support systems) determinants are interdependent, therefore reinforcing the utility of multi-theory integration for the understanding of emotional health within marginalized populations. By testing this model in the context of a developing country, it also brings out the cross-cultural applicability of these Western-developed theories. This sets an impetus for further comparative studies across different contexts on the globe.

The results have great implications for policy, mental health intervention, and community development, especially in urban places like Karachi. The very strong negative effect of not having enough social support indicates an immediate need for strengthening community-based resources, such as support groups, NGOs, or workplace policies for single mothers. The findings suggest that policymakers should introduce targeted welfare programs, mental health services, and subsidies for childcare in single-parent households. Also, such policies should cover interventions focused on stress reduction, such as cognitive behavioral therapy, building resilience, and mindfulness programs, which can reduce the emotional toll taken on single mothers, particularly those with low relational support. Flexible arrangements from learning institutions and employers would not only help single mothers reduce their stress but also lead to better emotional outcomes. In summary, the study provides an evidence base, which though already robust, can be used to develop interventions at multiple levels in economically and culturally sensitive settings to enhance the psychological well-being of single mothers.

5.2. Limitations and Future Research Directions

Though very valuable, this study is not without limitations. First, it used a cross-sectional design, so the type of model used can only show the direction of relationships. Better data to show how time elapses would have been a longitudinal study on stress and emotional well-being in single mothers. Second, it used self-reported measures, so there is a high probability of both social desirability and recall biases, especially in a conservative society like Pakistan, where the revelation of emotional difficulties or stress within the family can earn stigma. Third, it was conducted in Karachi, and the sample was drawn from an urban, relatively more resource-rich set-up; the experiences of single mothers in rural or less-developed regions could be entirely different due to the less or non-availability of various social infrastructures, including cultural norms and services. Finally, single motherhood was treated as a unidimensional construct; the stratification by type (e.g., widowed, divorced, never-married) could mask different emotional and social challenges that different subgroups may pose.

Future research should use longitudinal or panel data designs to establish the direction of causality and changes over time. In addition, the use of qualitative interviews as part of a mixed-method approach would provide a better understanding of the lived experiences and contextual coping strategies of single mothers. It would be interesting to investigate the effects of such factors as the education level, income, or age of the child, and support from extended family members, as potential moderators of the relationship between stress and support. Comparative analyses of data from various provinces in Pakistan could shed more light on the regional variations of maternal mental health. In addition, future studies can be based on intervention-based trials that can assess the efficacy of particular social or psychological support programs in improving the emotional outcomes of single mothers in a developing country.

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